

FACTORS INFLUENCING THE PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN WITH DIFFERENT TEMPERAMENTS

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the developmental stages and emotional changes in preschool-aged children.

During the preschool education period, which encompasses a child's physical development from ages 3 to 7, significant changes also occur in their psychological development. Throughout this period, the characteristics that define a child's personality are formed. From the perspective of a child's development as an individual, the preschool age can be divided into three stages:

The first stage includes 3-4 years, and this stage is associated with the strengthening of emotional self-control in a child.

The second stage - the period up to the age of 4-5 years, mainly moral self-control is strengthened.

The third stage covers 6-7 years of age and is characterized by the formation of business skills, self-awareness, and personality traits.

From the point of view of this periodization, the first and second stages correspond to the age of junior and middle kindergarten, and the 3rd stage corresponds to the age of senior kindergarten.

Conditions necessary for the development of a child's personality. As the child develops, he acquires new mental qualities and behavioral manifestations. In this way, he becomes a person, a small member of society. A child of preschool age is considered to be a person who has not yet fully formed and is able to mature later, but despite this, a relatively stable inner world is formed in the child, which can be the basis for calling the child a person for the first time.

Developmental conditions of preschool children are significantly different from the previous age stage. The requirements for the child's behavior by adults increase significantly. Compliance with moral rules and norms of social decency, which are mandatory for everyone in society, becomes the main requirement. The growth of opportunities to know the environment takes the child out of the narrow circle formed by relatives and begins to master the form of mutual relations for the first time. For the first time, the child learns the form of

mutual relations in the main activities of adults, such as education and work. The child plays with his peers, learns to coordinate his actions with the actions of his peers, to take into account the interests and opinions of his peers in the process of activity. Changes and difficulties occur in the child's actions during the period of preschool childhood. They demand not only the child's perception, thinking, memory, but also his behavior. The acquisition of morals in interpersonal relations is managed under the influence of adults. This is the main influence of adults on the formation of a child's personality.

The development of a child's personality includes two aspects. One of them means that the child gradually understands the environment and feels his place in it. Because of these, changes in the child's behavior occur, and under their influence, the child performs one or another action. Another aspect requires the development of feelings and will.

They ensure the impact of the above-mentioned changes, stability of behavior, and its non-dependence on external conditions. As an example of manners for children, adults are served primarily by their actions and interactions. The behavior of close people around the child has a direct and serious impact on him. He tends to imitate them, imitate their habits, assimilate their thoughts about people, events, and things. But the work is not limited to relatives.

Preschool children learn about the lives of adults in various ways: they observe their work, listen to stories, poems and fairy tales. People who receive love, respect and praise from others serve as role models for the child. At the same time, the actions of his peers, who are positively evaluated and popular in the children's group, can be an example for him.

Children themselves and others gradually begin to evaluate their actions based on the idea of behavior expected of them. Children in the junior and middle groups learn the rules of cultural and hygienic skills, rules for observing rules and dealing with toys.

They obey the demands of adults and try to have rules. They complain to the kindergarten teacher about the violation of the rules of conduct by their peers. In most cases, such complaints are not a complaint, but a specific request, that compliance with the rule is mandatory for everyone. Learning the rules of interaction with other children in early and middle age is of primary importance.

The obligation to take into account the opinion of a friend, his rights and wishes often complicates children's activities. Learning the rules of interaction is not easy for children, without understanding the nature of a specific situation, children initially accept these rules officially. By actually changing, breaking and restoring the rules of behavior by them, children gain experience.

After the emotional attitude of adults towards the child as a "good boy" and the initial adaptation to his own gender, a new social environment is formed in the child, that is, a desire to meet the demands of adults and to be recognized appears. . Spiritual feeling and conscience are positive aspects of the desire to gain respect. Conscience is explained by the word "should" in people's daily relationships.

Through education, the sense of perfection, which is the highest achievement of human spiritual culture, becomes the achievement of a specific person. Knowledge acquired by the child on the moral formation of the person; moral behavior acquired during communication with people around, emotional experiences of gains and losses during interaction with people.

During the preschool period, the level of consciousness changes, and as a result, children begin to follow moral rules. Children of junior and middle kindergarten age get used to following the rules, and sometimes even have an "excessive love of order" and cannot tolerate even minor violations of the rules. When approaching school age, following the usual rule becomes a conscious act.

During this period, children not only begin to obey the rules themselves, but also monitor that other children follow them. The development of pride and shyness in children of junior and middle kindergarten age is of great importance in learning moral examples and rules. The child is forced to coordinate his actions with the assessments and praises given by adults. A child of this age feels pride not only for the support of adults, but also for his positive qualities (courage, honesty, willingness to share with others). He measures his actions against a positive role model, with whom he understands that similarity can give him a reason to be proud of himself. Shyness grows in a child due to the direct involvement of adults in his affairs in the early childhood. Shyness in a preschool child occurs even when he realizes that he has acted worse than others expect, more precisely, breaking the rules, deviating from a positively evaluated example.

The child is also ashamed of the manifestation of cowardice, rudeness, anger, blindness, etc. At the age of junior and middle kindergarten, the child's dependence on adults remains the same as before. The behavior of an adult causes the activity of a child to become more active. It has been found that when an adult can lean on a child, share his successes and grieve his losses, the child will always feel refreshed and ready to take action and overcome obstacles even in bad times. .

The other part of the children, on the contrary, increases the speed of work, but despite this, the work efficiency is low. An adult's openly negative attitude towards a child causes the usual reactions in him: the child either tries to break the barrier of alienation, establish contact with an adult, or becomes preoccupied with himself and avoids communication. tries to escape. According to the data, the thirst for the love of another person and the desire to give love to someone is a first-order, very necessary need. A child's love for his mother occupies a special place in this regard. All his needs are fulfilled through the mother, because she is the source of the child's joy, sense of protection and emotional peace.

Kindness and benevolence create conditions for the development of positive qualities in a child. Distance from him, anger, and even a slight neglect of adults, causes the child to avoid unpleasant feelings and to preoccupy with himself. Adult alienation can create the basis for the development of the following negative traits: antipathy, aggression, lying, greed, laziness and submissiveness.

An adult should carefully choose the emotional relationships of influencing a child. The method of positive and negative influence on the child should not be used casually (depending on the mood of an adult), but should become a special tool of treatment. Positive feelings form the atmosphere of treatment, and alienation should be used in the form of a reprimand for a child's serious mistake.

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